

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

Report on the ESDM runtime extensions for parallel in-flight analytics

Deliverable D5.1

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Title image

Visualisation produced with ParaView from the PAV experiment presented in Figure 6. It shows the yearly average of the near-surface air temperature (*tasmx* variable) in Kelvin degrees. The experiment is applied to a subset of the CMCC-ESM2 [1] CMIP6 dataset [2] from 2015 to 2020 (*SSP585* experiment). See Section 4.5.4 for more details on the overall PAV experiment definition.

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	Page	
	2	

Content

1. Abstract /publishable summary	5
2. Conclusion & Results	5
3. Project objectives	6
4. Detailed report on the deliverable	7
4.1. Overview, background and motivations of the ESDM-PAV Runtime	7
4.2. ESDM-PAV Runtime design	9
4.3. ESDM-PAV Experiment Schema	10
4.3.1. Experiment flow control	14
4.3.2. Check ESDM data availability extension	19
4.3.3. Experiment resilience	22
4.3.4. Experiment checkpoint	25
4.4. ESDM-PAV Runtime implementation	28
4.4.1. PAV tasks management	29
4.4.2. Integration with HPC schedulers	32
4.5. ESDM-PAV Python module	33
4.5.1. Experiment modelling	34
4.5.2. Execution management	37
4.5.3. Python CLI	39
4.5.4. Test cases	39
4.6. In-flight analytics via ESDM	42
4.7. PAV plugin implementation	45
4.8. Software setup	47
4.8.1. Portability of the solution	48
4.8.2. Setup of the ESDM-PAV Runtime	48
4.8.3. Installation of the ESDM-PAV Python Client	50
5. Abbreviations and acronyms	51
6. References (<i>Bibliography</i>)	52
7. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	54
8. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC	54
9. Sustainability	54
10. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results	55
10.1. Target audience	55
10.2. Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable	55

Deliverable D5.1 ESIWACE2 Project

10.3.	Publications in preparation OR submitted	56
10.4.	Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable	56

1. Abstract /publishable summary

As the volumes of data produced by *Earth-System Models* (ESM) continue to increase, solutions capable of addressing *post-processing, analysis and visualisation* (PAV) of these data at extreme-scale are required. Novel technologies supporting parallel data I/O and processing for different scientific domains are, thus, being developed. For example, the *Earth System Data Middleware* (ESDM), developed in the context of the ESIWACE CoE for climate and weather applications, aims to provide improved I/O towards heterogeneous storage back-ends.

The *ESDM-PAV runtime*, reported in this document, provides the extensions to the ESDM middleware with the goal of specifically supporting PAV needs in the field of climate and weather applications. It delivers a simple high-level interface to build PAV experiments composed of different tools, as well as integrating with the HPC software ecosystem. It is built on top of the ESDM software used for *I/O* and *in-flight analytics* purposes. The proposed solution allows the support of different types of execution parallelism, exploiting a *task-based programming abstraction*, whereas the *in-flight analytics extensions* allow performing the analysis while the data are being accessed, potentially offloading the processing on the storage systems, therefore reducing data movement between storage and computing resources.

This deliverable provides the formal documentation of the final release of the ESDM-PAV runtime: its complete design, the parallelisation strategies employed and the software implemented. It describes the approach considered to support efficient *in-flight analytics* on top of the ESDM, as well as the integration strategy for PAV applications. It also presents a set of usage examples of the supported features and the related system documentation.

2. Conclusion & Results

The ESDM-PAV runtime presented in this document, including the related parallelisation strategies for PAV applications and the extensions for in-flight analytics on top of the ESDM system, aim to support scientific data-centric scenarios with a focus on the field of climate and weather. In particular, the proposed solution is designed to take advantage of HPC infrastructures by scaling with the size of the computing resources available and/or needed by the applications. The proposed multi-node approach allows, in fact, (i) transparent distribution of computation over multiple nodes and (ii) system integration with HPC-based batch scheduler solutions. In-flight analytics have been considered at the level of PAV applications to reduce data movement from storage to the computing nodes and to improve I/O efficiency.

The runtime provides several features to control the execution flow, address execution resilience, support both data and control flow approaches, and interact with heterogeneous storage systems via the ESDM.

Effort has been also devoted to simplifying the experiment definition and execution from the researcher point of view, by providing a high-level Python-based interface. To further address usability, the Python modules have been developed to allow users to easily integrate their features in Jupyter Notebooks.

An initial set of example use cases has been defined and tested to validate the runtime features. Other use cases, at larger-scale, will be implemented in the rest of the project to fully evaluate the implemented

	Page	
	5	

software solution and its interaction with data produced by large ESM simulations. Finally, it is noteworthy that, although what is presented in this document represents the final version of the ESDM-PAV runtime system, further extensions, as well as bug fixing and improvements to the system will be taken into account until the end of the project.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	X
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1. Overview, background and motivations of the ESDM-PAV Runtime

This deliverable represents the documentation of the implemented *Earth-System Data Middleware* (ESDM) runtime extensions for *post-processing, analytics and visualisation* (PAV). It describes the strategies employed for parallel execution of PAV applications and the support for in-flight analytics on top of the ESDM system, as well as the related software components implemented. It also reports the main features and abstractions available to manage PAV applications, providing some simple usage examples, together with the pointers to the code on GitHub.

In order to effectively support knowledge extraction from large data volumes, specialised software components are required to efficiently exploit parallel I/O and computation for scientific analysis and visualisation applications [3]. To this end, the ESDM system¹ developed in the context of the ESIWACE CoE, can provide improved parallel data access for PAV use cases in the field of Earth System Modelling (ESM).

The *ESDM-PAV runtime*, which builds on top of the ESDM system, aims to further support PAV applications at scale. In particular, the runtime provides the features to efficiently support large-scale parallel PAV workflows by exploiting a *task-based programming model* to manage complex execution graphs. This approach allows modelling PAV applications that consist of multiple analytics tasks connected through a set of data and control flow dependencies, also called *PAV experiments* in the rest of the document. The experiments defined can consist of very complex structures, ranging from simple sequences of tasks to complex *directed acyclic graphs* (DAG) of tasks. Tasks can potentially be very heterogeneous in terms of type of function applied, compute resources required and execution time span.

To implement task-based execution and parallelism, PAV experiments are defined following a workflow-oriented paradigm. This allows scientists to describe the steps of the scientific analysis and the flow between them in a text document, leaving the intricate coordination, automation and optimisation of the execution to the software system. Thus, workflow management solutions can effectively support scientists in data-centric research [4].

The workflow management technologies for eScience available in literature are varied and they all differ from each other in many respects, as for example in terms of definition languages, workflow representation, and execution models [5]. Each scientific domain tends to employ specific workflow management solutions [6][7], with *Cylc* [8] being one of the systems adopted by the climate and weather community, e.g., for forecasting systems.

However, as the size of applications is growing, with data becoming a central component of the applications, multiple challenges must be faced to support future workflows at extreme-scale [6]. Some of the challenges for extreme-scale workflow systems related to this document include: usability of the solution to simplify its adoption for large applications; workflow resiliency and error management; dynamic resource provisioning, management and scheduling; support for advanced and heterogenous storage solutions; monitoring of complex workflow execution [9].

¹ Earth-System Data Middleware: <https://github.com/ESIWACE/esdm>

	Page	
	7	

The proposed solution tries to address some of these challenges, however, it is worth mentioning that it does not aim to represent an end-to-end workflow system, but rather to support the data post-processing, analytics and visualisation phase by exploiting a task-based programming approach commonly used in workflow management systems. Thus, with respect to other workflow solutions, it represents a more *specialised and light-weight solution tailored for PAV applications*, providing (i) *a unified and simple interface to build and manage large-scale PAV applications*, (ii) *integrated with the HPC infrastructure for efficiently running data-oriented applications on top of compute-oriented scheduling systems*, (iii) *as well as coupled with the ESDM system for I/O and in-flight analytics*.

Under these assumptions, a PAV application could for instance represent a sub-task of larger ESM workflow, managed by an end-to-end solution, such as the aforementioned Cylc, with the ESDM-PAV runtime acting as a specialised system to support the more data-oriented PAV applications, while the ESDM middleware provides a bridge between data produced from simulations and data processed by the ESDM-PAV. The extensions for in-flight analytics will then support reduced data movement.

More in detail, the task-based parallelism approach is implemented by the runtime system, which analyses the PAV experiment definition and schedules the different tasks to be executed concurrently according to the dependencies specification. In this way, the runtime system will automatically identify the proper execution plan and ensure that independent tasks will run in parallel when possible, simplifying the management of very complex PAV applications from the end-user point of view.

To tackle large scale PAV scenarios, the runtime system supports execution of tasks distributed across different compute nodes in HPC infrastructures by interacting with HPC batch schedulers, such as LSF [10] or SLURM [11]. Moreover, besides concurrent execution of individual tasks, each task can still be executed in parallel by using multi-threading and multi-processing when implemented by the PAV application. Hence, the runtime supports multiple types of parallelisation strategies, i.e., task parallelism, data parallelism, inter-task parallelisation. Additionally, it takes into account fault tolerance and recovery of the experiment execution by providing specific actions in case of operator errors and checkpoints for restarting the experiment.

Usability in the creation of PAV experiments and their execution has been addressed through the development of a Python-based high-level interface. This module also supports monitoring of the execution progress and can be directly used within the user-friendly Jupyter Notebooks [12] software.

The ESDM, as previously mentioned, has been integrated in the PAV runtime to support improved data access to heterogeneous storage devices. Additionally, the ESDM interface has been extended, as reported in milestone MS4.1 [13], which allows reading streams of data and applying low-level kernels in a map-reduce way during the process, with the aim of reducing data movement between the components. This interface represents the foundations for the in-flight analytics extensions integrated in the Ophidia analytics framework and reported in this deliverable. Thanks to the interface, the computation could be potentially offloaded to the storage system, if the required functionality is offered.

The next section, Section 4.2, provides an overview of the ESDM-PAV runtime design, reprised and updated from previous documents, while Section 4.3 comprehensively describes the features supported for the definition of PAV experiments and Section 4.4 delves into the implementation details of the runtime system.

Section 4.5 documents the features provided by the Python client module and shows some usage examples. Section 4.6 and Section 4.7 describe, respectively, the approach used for in-flight analytics and for the integration of PAV applications. Finally, Section 4.8 provides an overview of the steps required to set up the ESDM-PAV runtime components.

4.2. ESDM-PAV Runtime design

Starting from the ESDM-PAV design introduced in ESIWACE2 milestone MS5.1 [14], and further refined in milestone MS4.1 [13], the ESDM-PAV runtime and related client tools have been developed to support the execution of PAV experiments. Previous versions of the software have been already briefly described in the related release reports [15][16]. This document reprises and extends these reports to provide a consistent and updated view of the implemented software in its current version (v1.4).

Figure 1 shows an updated version of the ESDM-PAV software architecture: PAV experiments can be defined by the users through the PAV experiment schema in JSON format (described in Section 4.3), using the different features provided by the ESDM-PAV runtime. The Python API is used to model the experiment and manage its execution on the runtime system (see Section 4.5). With respect to what was originally planned, a Python API has been chosen in place of a C-based one because of the higher usability and interoperability with widely-used Python solutions, such as Jupyter Notebooks, and the wide adoption of Python in the weather and climate community.

Once the experiment has been submitted, the runtime will take care of scheduling the execution of the different PAV operators composing the experiment, supporting distributed execution in parallel on multiple nodes, as well as monitoring the progress, handling errors, transferring intermediate results among tasks, interrupting the execution, as reported in Section 4.4. The robustness of the experiment execution can be controlled by the developer through a set of error management and recovery features.

As already stated, the proposed runtime system has been designed specifically to address PAV needs by supporting operations from different PAV applications in the experiments. In particular, it supports some PAV target applications consisting of: *Ophidia* [17] operators, *Climate Data Operators (CDO)* [18] and generic command line interfaces, which allow, for example, the integration of visualisation tools such as *ParaView* [19]; a strong integration strategy with the runtime has been employed for *Ophidia* and *CDO*. All these software solutions, from the I/O perspective, have been integrated and tested with the ESDM system within WP4, as reported in deliverable D4.1 [20].

The ESDM interface provides improved data access to heterogeneous storage back-ends. Its extended interface is integrated into the software stack to (i) manage the experiment execution based on ESDM data availability and (ii) to allow the execution of analytics kernels through the streaming interfaces, potentially offloading the computation to the storage back-ends when active-storage kernels are available. In particular, the in-flight analytics extensions in *Ophidia* are based on this second feature (described in Section 4.6). The set of kernels developed within the project will be detailed in deliverable D5.2. It will include simple operations that can benefit from reduced data movement thanks to storage offloading, such as operations for selection, statistical analysis and mathematical functions that can be executed in parallel, as well as more complex operations, such as transformations and interpolations, that can take advantage of massively-parallel architectures like GPUs.

	Page	
	9	

Figure 1. Refined ESDM-PAV software architecture

4.3. ESDM-PAV Experiment Schema

The ESDM-PAV *experiment schema* has been defined in order to support the definition and execution of PAV experiments composed of different tools. It represents the experiment definition language providing the constructs for specifying PAV workflows in terms of tasks and dependencies. Users and developers can create *PAV experiment documents* by exploiting this schema.

The format adopted to implement these documents is the *JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)*, which represents a widely used, language-independent format providing a flexible way for specifying data in a human-readable way. Since the PAV application requirements are similar to those of the Ophidia framework (one of the target systems being integrated into the ESDM-PAV runtime), which has its own Workflow Management System (WfMS), the format has been inspired based on the Ophidia workflow schema².

Listing 1 shows the definition of the experiment schema supported by the ESDM-PAV runtime. It shows the available abstractions to describe experiment tasks, dependencies and options to control resilience, through a set of keywords. An experiment can be considered as a list of “*task*” JSON objects, each one consisting of the following main keywords:

² Ophidia JSON Request Schema: http://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/users/appendix/json_request.html

- **name:** the name given to the specific task to identify it. It is a mandatory field and its value must be unique within the whole *PAV document*;
- **type:** type of task to be executed (e.g., PAV tool/system, flow control construct);
- **operator:** a mandatory field specifying the operator name to be executed;
- **arguments:** an optional list of values describing the input arguments for the specified operator;
- **dependencies:** an optional list of tasks (parents) that have to be completed before the execution of the given task (child);
- **on_error:** an optional field used to set the operation to be carried out in case of task failure;
- **checkpoint:** an optional field used to set a checkpoint.

With respect to the version previously presented in MS4.1, the schema has been refined in order to simplify the interface; to this end, the “*outputs*” and “*inputs*” keywords, defined at task level, have been moved to the level of the “*arguments*” keyword, as admissible arguments. In this way, the “input” and “output” arguments can be specified when required by the particular task using the format shown in Listing 2 (in Line 12 or 13). The rest of the schema follows the structure defined in MS4.1. Additional keywords, such as “*abstract*”, are also available to describe the overall experiment.

```

1  {
2  "schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-04/schema#",
3  "title": "pav_experiment_schema",
4  "description": "PAV Experiment Document JSON Schema",
5  "type": "object",
6  "properties":
7  {
8    "name": {"type": "string", "description": "experiment name"},
9    "author": {"type": "string", "description": "experiment author"},
10   "abstract": {"type": "string", "description": "experiment description"},
11   "nthreads": {"type": "string", "description": "number of threads for the
entire experiment"},
12   "tasks":
13   {
14     "type": "array",
15     "description": "task list representing the experiment",
16     "items":
17     {
18       "type": "object",
19       "description": "task with its properties",
20       "properties":
21       {
22         "name": {"type": "string", "description": "unique task name"},
23         "type": {"type": "string", "description": "type of PAV tool to run"},
24         "operator": {"type": "string", "description": "Operator name"},
25         "arguments": { "type": "array",
26           "description": "list of user-defined operator arguments as key=value
pairs",
27           "items": {"type": "string", "description": "format to use:
keyX=valueX"},
           "uniqueItems": true},
28       }
29     }
30   }
31 }

```

```

28     "dependencies":
29     {
30         "type": "array",
31         "description": "list of tasks on which the current task depends",
32         "items":
33         {
34             "type": "object",
35             "description": "dependency for a specific argument of the current
36             task",
37             "properties":
38             {
39                 "task": {"type": "string", "description": "task name which the
40                 current argument depends on"},
41                 "argument": {"type": "string", "default": "cube", "description":
42                 "argument name depending on the output of the task specified in 'task' field"}
43             },
44             "required": ["task"]
45         },
46         "uniqueItems": true
47     },
48     "on_error":
49     {
50         "type": "string",
51         "default": "abort",
52         "description": "behaviour in case of error: skip, continue, abort
53         or repeat execution"
54     },
55     "checkpoint":
56     {
57         "type": "string",
58         "default": "none",
59         "description": "name of the checkpoint to be saved in case the task
60         is successfully completed"
61     },
62     "required": ["name", "operator"],
63     "additionalProperties": false
64 }

```

Listing 1. Definition of the ESDM-PAV Schema

The “*type*” field can be used to specify the tool for task execution (e.g. Ophidia or CDO), thus classifying tasks on a per-application basis, as well as to identify tasks that “*control*” the flow execution, as reported more in detail in the next section, as for example: iterative loops, parallel branches, selection statements, waits for data availability, etc. Table 1 summarises the set of values allowed for the field “*type*” and the corresponding

	Page	
	12	

meaning. The ESDM-PAV Python interface, in the current version, supports all the different types of tasks defined in the table, by mapping the required arguments directly to the JSON format.

Table 1. Possible task *type* values supported by the ESDM-PAV schema

Task type	The task is	The field “operator” is	Example
ophidia (default)	Ophidia operator	operator name	"type": "ophidia", "operator": "oph_importesdm"
cdo	chain of one or more CDO operators	chain specification	"type": "cdo", "operator": "- remapbil,grid_file"
generic	bash command	bash command	"type": "generic", "operator": "cp", "args": "a.nc b.nc"
control	flow control operator	operator name	"type": "control", "operator": "for"

Example

Listing 2 shows a simple example of a PAV experiment document following the aforementioned schema. In particular, this example shows a sequential chain of four operations, both CDO- and Ophidia-based. The first task (Lines 7-15) defines a regridding operation performed with CDO on the file specified in the “*input*” argument, creating as “*output*” an ESDM container (the equivalent of a dataset in ESDM). The second one (Lines 16-27) imports the output of the first task in Ophidia; this is specified through the dependency on the task called “*Regrid*” (Lines 24-26). The third task (Lines 28-40) runs a data reduction operation through Ophidia on the data imported in the “*Import*” task, while the last one (41-51) exports the result of the “*Moving Avg*” task from Ophidia to the “*output*” ESDM data.

```

1  {
2    "name": "CDO and Ophidia PAV experiment example",
3    "author": "ESIWACE2",
4    "abstract": "Example of PAV workflow with CDO and Ophidia",
5    "tasks":
6    [
7      {
8        "name": "Regrid",
9        "type": "cdo",
10       "operator": "-remapbil,r90x45",
11       "arguments": [
12         "input=path/to/infile.nc",
13         "output=esdm://indata"
14       ]
15     },
16     {

```

```

17     "name": "Import",
18     "type": "ophidia",
19     "operator": "oph_importesdm",
20     "arguments": [
21       "measure=pr",
22       "ncores=$1"
23     ],
24     "dependencies": [
25       { "task": "Regrid", "argument": "input" }
26     ],
27   },
28   {
29     "name": "Moving avg",
30     "type": "ophidia",
31     "operator": "oph_apply",
32     "arguments": [
33       "query=oph_moving_avg(measure,7.0)",
34       "measure_type=auto",
35       "ncores=$1"
36     ],
37     "dependencies": [
38       { "task": "Import", "argument": "cube" }
39     ]
40   },
41   {
42     "name": "Export",
43     "type": "ophidia",
44     "operator": "oph_exportesdm",
45     "arguments": [
46       "output=esdm://outdata"
47     ],
48     "dependencies": [
49       { "task": "Moving avg", "argument": "cube" }
50     ]
51   }
52 ]
53 }

```

Listing 2. Example of PAV JSON document with CDO and Ophidia operators

4.3.1. Experiment flow control

As mentioned in the previous section, the “type” field can also be used to specify tasks that “control” the flow execution. Seven flow control “operators” are supported by the ESDM-PAV software:

- for-loop statement: the “for” and “endfor” constructs can be used to declare an iterative loop, when a set of tasks (i.e., a sub-workflow) has to be executed more times during the same experiment in order to improve, for instance, intermediate approximate solutions of an iterative method. Loops can also be nested;

- if-else statement (“if”, “elseif”, “else” and “endif”): these flow control constructs are used to declare a selection statement. In particular, the operator “if” can be adopted in case a sub-workflow should be executed only when a given condition is met during the execution, while the “else” construct is used when an alternative sub-workflow has to be executed if the condition is not met; the “elseif” construct is adopted in case another condition needs to be verified for the execution of the alternative sub-workflow. Also in this case the construct can be nested;
- waiting statement (“wait”): this construct is used to defer the execution of the dependent tasks. Deferring time can be fixed, thus introducing an additional delay, or depending on a condition. The statement is adopted to check the availability of a file or an ESDM dataset before trying to process it. More details on this specific abstraction are provided in Section 4.3.2.

The definitions of these constructs have been inherited from the corresponding Ophidia operators³ and their interfaces and implementations have been adapted to address ESDM-PAV runtime requirements and integrate the ESDM interface, as in the case of the wait construct.

An interesting feature provided by the loop (“for” - “endfor”) statement is the support for “parallel branches”. In this case, it is assumed the sub-workflow has to be applied (i) on different input datasets or (ii) on the same dataset but using different arguments in tasks composing the sub-workflow. Hence the ESDM-PAV runtime will replicate the sub-workflow into *multiple branches* before running the experiment, with the number of branches specified before experiment execution. Of course, branches can also be executed in parallel, provided that computational resources are available. It is noteworthy that this approach based on parallel branches is quite common in different types of analysis where multiple datasets have to be processed within the same experiment, e.g., for ensemble and multi-model analysis.

Examples

Listing 3 shows an example use case of a PAV experiment in JSON format where the operators “for” and “endfor” are used to define a number of “parallel branches”, each corresponding to the application of a CDO operator to a different dataset (e.g., evaluation of the meridional mean value). The “parallel=yes” argument (Line 13) allows the activation of the parallel branch execution mode. For each branch, the name of the input ESDM container (Line 21) and the corresponding output (Line 22) are determined by the argument “index” of the operator “for”, so that the pairs “input_container_1” and “output_container_1” are related to the first branch, the pairs “input_container_2” and “output_container_2” are related to the second branch and so on. Note that the operator “endfor” has no arguments (Lines 28-35).

```

1  {
2      "name": "Example of parallel branches",
3      "author": "ESiWACE2",
4      "tasks":
5      [
6          {
7              "name": "Begin loop",

```

³ Ophidia flow control operators:
<http://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/users/operators/index.html#workflow-management>

```

8         "type": "control",
9         "operator": "for",
10        "arguments": [
11            "key=index",
12            "counter=1:3",
13            "parallel=yes"
14        ]
15    },
16    {
17        "name": "Apply operation",
18        "type": "cdo",
19        "operator": "mermean",
20        "arguments": [
21            "input=esdm://input_container_{index}",
22            "output=esdm://output_container_{index}"
23        ],
24        "dependencies": [
25            { "task": "Begin loop" }
26        ]
27    },
28    {
29        "name": "End loop",
30        "type": "control",
31        "operator": "endfor",
32        "dependencies": [
33            { "task": "Apply operation" }
34        ]
35    }
36 ]
37 }

```

Listing 3. Example of use of the parallel branches on different input datasets

The same approach could also be applied to run different operations on the same file. Listing 4 shows a PAV experiment example where the “for” and “endfor” operators are applied in such a way that the same dataset (“input_container”, Line 21) is the input for different CDO operators (*zonmax*, *zonmin* and *zonavg*), producing different output ESDM containers (Line 22). Note the use of argument “values” (Line 12) to associate a different operator with each branch (Line 19).

```

1    {
2        "name": "Example of parallel branches",
3        "author": "ESiWACE2",
4        "tasks":
5        [
6            {
7                "name": "Begin loop",
8                "type": "control",
9                "operator": "for",
10               "arguments": [

```

```

11         "key=index",
12         "values=max|min|avg",
13         "parallel=yes"
14     ]
15 },
16 {
17     "name": "Apply operation",
18     "type": "cdo",
19     "operator": "zon@{index}",
20     "arguments": [
21         "input=esdm://input_container",
22         "output=esdm://container_with_{index}_values"
23     ],
24     "dependencies": [
25         { "task": "Begin loop" }
26     ]
27 },
28 {
29     "name": "End loop",
30     "type": "control",
31     "operator": "endfor",
32     "dependencies": [
33         { "task": "Apply operation" }
34     ]
35 }
36 ]
37 }

```

Listing 4. Example of use of the parallel branches on different input datasets and with different operators

Listing 5 reports an example of usage of the “if”, “else” and “endif” constructs to select the operation for application to the input dataset, either a CDO or an Ophidia operator. The first parameter \$1 of the PAV experiment (Line 11) is used to select the branch to be executed, whereas the second parameter \$2 represents the input ESDM container in case of CDO (Line 19), or the PID of the input datacube in case of Ophidia (Line 39). This example shows how a PAV experiment can be coded to support different execution paths which can then be selected at run-time according to the required processing. Note that:

- the operators “else” and “endif” have no arguments;
- the operator “endif” must depend on the last task of each selection branch (line 51 and 52).

```

1  {
2      "name": "Example of selection",
3      "author": "ESiWACE2",
4      "tasks":
5      [
6          {
7              "name": "Begin selection",
8              "type": "control",
9              "operator": "if",

```

```

10         "arguments": [
11             "condition=$1"
12         ]
13     },
14     {
15         "name": "Apply CDO operation",
16         "type": "cdo",
17         "operator": "timavg",
18         "arguments": [
19             "input=$2",
20             "output=esdm://container"
21         ],
22         "dependencies": [
23             { "task": "Begin selection" }
24         ]
25     },
26     {
27         "name": "Else",
28         "type": "control",
29         "operator": "else",
30         "dependencies": [
31             { "task": "Begin selection" }
32         ]
33     },
34     {
35         "name": "Apply Ophidia operation",
36         "type": "ophidia",
37         "operator": "oph_reduce",
38         "arguments": [
39             "cube=$2",
40             "operation=avg"
41         ],
42         "dependencies": [
43             { "task": "Else" }
44         ]
45     },
46     {
47         "name": "End selection",
48         "type": "control",
49         "operator": "endif",
50         "dependencies": [
51             { "task": "Apply CDO operation" },
52             { "task": "Apply Ophidia operation" }
53         ]
54     }
55 ]
56 }

```

Listing 5. Example of use of “if”, “else” and “endif” constructs

4.3.2. Check ESDM data availability extension

In some applications like for in-situ analytics, data processing can begin during data production, before the dataset is completely stored. Consider, for example, the simulation of a model: the generation and, then, the visualisation of a map representing the output data related to a given time step could begin while the data related to the next time steps are still being produced.

In case of ESDM containers and datasets, this “pipeline” from data production to post-processing and visualisation could be set up, provided that the ESDM library i) allows loading fragments of a dataset while other fragments of the same dataset are being stored and ii) includes appropriate *probing functions* to be used to check the availability of

- a container (e.g., the whole file);
- a dataset (e.g., a single variable);
- a subset of a dataset (e.g. a “region”), defined as a N-dimensional data subset.

These functions would enable ESDM-PAV runtime to handle the following workflow:

1. periodically check the availability of the piece of dataset to be processed;
2. load the target data as soon as they are available;
3. execute the operations required by the user;
4. store/visualise the results.

In order to handle this type of workflows, the ESDM library has been extended with the following probing functions⁴ whose meaning is trivial: each of them returns 1 if the target data exist.

```
int esdm_container_probe(const char *name);
int esdm_dataset_probe(const char *container_name,
                      const char *dataset_name);
int esdm_dataset_probe_region(const char *container_name,
                             const char *dataset_name,
                             esdm_dataspace_t * region);
```

These functions have been used to implement the wait statement introduced in Section 4.3.1. The related “wait” operator provides the features to check the availability of an ESDM dataset or a subset according to one or more dimensions, and blocks the execution of dependent tasks until data become available. A “wait” task can thus perform periodic controls (with a configurable polling time) to probe for ESDM data availability before starting any dependent task.

The next listing (Listing 6) shows an example of a PAV experiment where the waiting statement is used to check the availability of a portion of data related to a specific time step before loading it; the probing period is 1 second (Line 22). Whenever a time slice is found, an Ophidia-based task is executed to convert it into a datacube and it is further processed. The external loop (actually more parallel branches, Line 13) is used to

⁴ Note that the current implementation of these functions has not been optimized yet but they were included in ESDM to provide initial support for data probing and to allow optimization in future versions.

change the target time step (starting from index 1 to 10, Line 12), thus processing all the time slices of the input dataset.

To identify a time slice, the waiting task needs the dimension name called “*subset_dims*” (Line 25) and the application of a filter to select the subset called “*subset_filter*” (Line 26): in this case, the counter defined for the external loop (“*index*”) is used as a filter. This selection approach (i.e. the format to set the subset filter), also adopted for the operator OPH_IMPORTESDM (Lines 38 and 39), is compliant with other Ophidia operators that apply data filters. The counter “*index*” is also used to set the names of output ESDM containers (Line 62). During the execution, this type of waiting task exploits the probing function *esdm_dataset_probe_region*. Of course, if the “*wait*” statement is only used to check the availability of the ESDM container or dataset, the waiting task exploits the other probing functions, *esdm_container_probe* and *esdm_dataset_probe* respectively.

```

1  {
2      "name": "Example of probing task",
3      "author": "ESiWACE2",
4      "tasks":
5      [
6          {
7              "name": "Loop",
8              "type": "control",
9              "operator": "for",
10             "arguments": [
11                 "key=index",
12                 "counter=1:10",
13                 "parallel=yes"
14             ]
15         },
16         {
17             "name": "Wait",
18             "type": "control",
19             "operator": "wait",
20             "arguments": [
21                 "type=file",
22                 "timeout=1",
23                 "output=esdm://container",
24                 "measure=dataset",
25                 "subset_dims=time",
26                 "subset_filter=@index"
27             ],
28             "dependencies": [
29                 { "task": "Loop" }
30             ]
31         },
32         {
33             "name": "Import",
34             "type": "ophidia",

```

```

35     "operator": "oph_importesdm",
36     "arguments": [
37         "measure=dataset",
38         "subset_dims=time",
39         "subset_filter=@index",
40         "imp_dim=lon"
41     ],
42     "dependencies": [
43         { "task": "Wait", "argument": "input" }
44     ]
45 },
46 {
47     "name": "Reduction",
48     "type": "ophidia",
49     "operator": "oph_reduce",
50     "arguments": [
51         "operation=avg"
52     ],
53     "dependencies": [
54         { "task": "Import", "argument": "cube" }
55     ]
56 },
57 {
58     "name": "Export",
59     "type": "ophidia",
60     "operator": "oph_exportesdm",
61     "arguments": [
62         "output=esdm://container_@index"
63     ],
64     "dependencies": [
65         { "task": "Reduction", "argument": "cube" }
66     ]
67 },
68 {
69     "name": "End loop",
70     "type": "control",
71     "operator": "endfor",
72     "dependencies": [
73         { "task": "Export" }
74     ]
75 }
76 ]
77 }

```

Listing 6. Example of use of “wait” construct to check availability of an ESDM dataset

4.3.3. Experiment resilience

As reported in Listing 1, regarding workflow resilience, ESDM-PAV runtime is able to perform one of the following automatic operations in case a *target* task results in error (option “on_error”):

- **skip**: the error is ignored and the task is considered successfully executed, so that the execution of dependent tasks is enabled; the workflow execution continues without considering the target task (whose final status will be *SKIPPED*);
- **continue**: the error does not cause the failure of the workflow, but all dependent tasks are not executed; the workflow execution continues without considering these tasks (whose final status will be *SKIPPED*) and can complete successfully, provided that no other errors are raised;
- **abort** (default): the error causes the failure of the entire workflow; the execution of concurrent tasks, running when the error is raised, continues but no other tasks are submitted;
- **repeat**: the error causes the re-submission of the task, using the same parameters, provided that a maximum number of submissions is not reached. In this case, a new error would cause the failure of the workflow similarly to the option “*abort*”.

It is assumed that the options *skip* and *continue* are used in case the target task may fail, raising a warning but without impacting on the overall workflow execution. For instance, in case the target task tries to create a folder that already exists on the file system, the task fails, but the workflow execution can continue.

By default, the failure of any task results in a workflow to be aborted, however the execution of a task can be repeated, even multiple times, before being considered as failed. In this case, the option *repeat* can be set. The rationale of these repetitions is that the task could fail because some (meta)data is not available when the execution begins, e.g., when an ESDM container due to be processed by the task does not contain a dataset because it is still being written to disk. Clearly, the task will usually have greater chance to result successful in case the repetition is deferred by a certain delay from the receipt of the error notification, hence ESDM-PAV runtime can wait for a backoff time before re-submitting the task. In addition, in case failures are due to a huge load for the compute nodes, backoff time could randomly be chosen aiming to reduce task bursts. For the same reasons, the maximum backoff time could increase after any failure. Of course, the backoff time could also be fixed or not considered at all.

Table 2 shows possible settings for the option “on_error” in case the target task has to be repeated before considering it as failed. Three additional arguments can follow the keyword “repeat”.

- The first argument is the maximum number of re-submissions to be tried before considering the task as failed. Note that setting the option “on_error” to “repeat 0” is equivalent to setting it to “abort”;
- The second argument is the maximum value *T* of backoff time (in seconds); by default it is 0, so that no delay is considered;
- If set, the third argument denotes the way to change the maximum backoff time after any re-submission: “*random*” means that the maximum *T* is not changed, whereas “*exponential*” means that *T* is doubled after any re-submission (thus reducing the load on the system). The delay will be then selected as a random integer value between 0 and (*T* - 1) seconds. Note that actual delay will always be equal to *T* seconds if this third argument is not set.

Table 2. Possible values for option “on_error” supported by the ESDM-PAV schema

Setting	Meaning in case the first submission results in error
"on_error": "repeat 2"	Target task is re-submitted as soon as possible. After 2 re-submissions resulting in error, the task is considered as failed.
"on_error": "repeat 4 5"	Target task is re-submitted after 5 seconds from the receipt of an error notification; backoff time is fixed for all the re-submissions. After 4 re-submissions resulting in error, the task is considered as failed.
"on_error": "repeat 6 10 random"	Target task is re-submitted after a random delay from 0 to 9 seconds from the receipt of error notification; backoff time can change from a re-submission to another one. After 6 re-submissions resulting in error, the task is considered as failed.
"on_error": "repeat 6 10 exponential"	Target task is re-submitted after a random delay from 0 to 9 s from the receipt of the first error notification. Then, the maximum backoff time is doubled, so that target task is re-submitted after a random delay from 0 to 19 s from the receipt of the second error notification, after a delay from 0 to 39 s from the third error notification and so on. After 6 re-submissions resulting in error, the task is considered as failed.

Listing 7 shows an example of an experiment using the option “on_error”. Since, for most tasks, the corresponding workflow must be aborted in case of failure, the option is set to “abort” in the header of the experiment description (Line 4), meaning that this error policy is followed for all tasks, unless the option “on_error” of the specific task indicates a different policy; this of course supersedes the globally defined behaviour. In particular, in case of failure of the task “Import” (Lines 7-17), the execution will be repeated up to three times before aborting the workflow and, in addition, ESDM-PAV runtime will wait for a random time between 0 and 9 seconds after receiving an error notification before re-submitting the task (Line 16), according to the behaviour described in Table 2. Finally, a possible failure of the task “CDO”, in this case, does not imply workflow failure as the option “on_error” is set to “skip” (Line 53).

```

1  {
2      "name": "Example of PAV experiment with resilience options",
3      "author": "ESiWACE2",
4      "on_error": "abort",
5      "tasks":
6      [
7          {
8              "name": "Import",
9              "type": "ophidia",
10             "operator": "oph_importesdm",
11             "arguments": [
12                 "input=esdm://container",
13                 "measure=variable_input",
14                 "imp_dim=time"

```

```

15         ],
16         "on_error": "repeat 3 10 random"
17     },
18     {
19         "name": "Reduce",
20         "type": "ophidia",
21         "operator": "oph_reduce",
22         "arguments": [
23             "operation=avg"
24         ],
25         "dependencies":
26         [
27             { "task": "Import", "argument": "cube" }
28         ]
29     },
30     {
31         "name": "Export",
32         "type": "ophidia",
33         "operator": "oph_exportnc",
34         "arguments": [
35             "output=file_ophidia_exported.nc"
36         ],
37         "dependencies":
38         [
39             { "task": "Reduce", "argument": "cube" }
40         ]
41     },
42     {
43         "name": "CDO",
44         "type": "cdo",
45         "operator": "selname,tos",
46         "arguments": [
47             "output=output.nc"
48         ],
49         "dependencies":
50         [
51             { "task": "Export", "argument": "input" }
52         ],
53         "on_error": "skip"
54     }
55 ]
56 }

```

Listing 7. Example of use of the option “on_error” to handle workflow resilience

4.3.4. Experiment checkpoint

In addition to the automatic operations performed during workflow execution in case of task failures, the user may also need to save the status of the workflow after a task is successfully completed, in order to be able to repeat the execution from a “consistent” intermediate state rather than from the beginning. In this way, the user can avoid wasting time and compute resources, and also recover the execution in case of critical errors. ESDM-PAV runtime offers this opportunity by allowing the user to set “checkpoints” in the experiment definition. The initial PAV experiment schema, presented in MS4.1, has therefore been extended to support the definition of checkpoints on given tasks, as shown at the beginning of Section 4.3.

A checkpoint is defined by a label assigned to a task using the option “*checkpoint*” of the JSON schema. Listing 8 reports an example of a PAV experiment with two checkpoints named “*imported*” and “*exported*” (Lines 15 and 40).

```

1  {
2      "name": "PAV experiment with checkpoints",
3      "author": "ESiWACE",
4      "tasks":
5      [
6          {
7              "name": "Import",
8              "type": "ophidia",
9              "operator": "oph_importesdm",
10             "arguments": [
11                 "input=esdm://input_container",
12                 "measure=variable_input",
13                 "imp_dim=time"
14             ],
15             "checkpoint": "imported"
16         },
17         {
18             "name": "Reduce",
19             "type": "ophidia",
20             "operator": "oph_reduce",
21             "arguments": [
22                 "operation=avg"
23             ],
24             "dependencies":
25             [
26                 { "task": "Import", "argument": "cube" }
27             ]
28         },
29         {
30             "name": "Export",
31             "type": "ophidia",
32             "operator": "oph_exportnc",
33             "arguments": [
34                 "output=file_ophidia_exported.nc"
35             ],

```

```

36         "dependencies":
37         [
38             { "task": "Reduce", "argument": "cube" }
39         ],
40         "checkpoint": "exported"
41     },
42     {
43         "name": "CDO",
44         "type": "cdo",
45         "operator": "oph_cdo",
46         "arguments": [
47             "command=-selname,tos",
48             "output=cdo_output.nc"
49         ],
50         "dependencies":
51         [
52             { "task": "Export", "argument": "input" }
53         ]
54     }
55 ]
56 }

```

Listing 8. Example of workflow with checkpoints

If a checkpoint is set, once the execution of the corresponding task is successfully completed (the checkpoint will be considered as *“passed”*), the ESDM-PAV runtime creates a PAV document starting from the original PAV experiment definition by dropping all the descriptions of the tasks already completed, and related dependencies. The runtime then saves the document appending the label to the original document file name. In this way, whenever users wish to repeat the PAV workflow execution from the checkpoint, they can simply submit this new PAV document.

With regards to the PAV experiment in the previous example, Listing 9 reports the description of the *“residual”* workflow after passing the checkpoint *“imported”*; note that some arguments are omitted to improve readability. The first task of the original experiment definition (*“Import”*) is clearly omitted. The *“Reduce”* task now includes the argument *“cube”* set to the identifier of the cube resulting from the omitted task *“Import”* (Line 12). The description of the other tasks is the same as the original experiment definition. The new experiment definition only reports reference to the checkpoints that have not been reached yet by the time the PAV document is created (Line 21).

```

1     {
2         "name": "PAV experiment with checkpoints",
3         "author": "ESiWACE",
4         ... // other omitted parameters
5         "tasks": [
6             {
7                 "name": "Reduce",
8                 "type": "ophidia",
9                 "operator": "oph_reduce",
10                "arguments": [

```

```

11         "operation=avg",
12         "cube=http://127.0.0.1/ophidia/57/38",
13         ... // other omitted parameters
14     ],
15     "dependencies": []
16 },
17 {
18     "name": "Export",
19     "type": "ophidia",
20     "operator": "oph_exportnc",
21     "checkpoint": "exported",
22     "arguments": [
23         "output=file_ophidia_exported.nc",
24         ... // other omitted parameters
25     ],
26     "dependencies": [
27         {
28             "argument": "cube",
29             "task": "Reduce",
30             ... // other omitted parameters
31         }
32     ]
33 },
34 {
35     "name": "CDO",
36     "type": "cdo",
37     "operator": "oph_cdo",
38     "arguments": [
39         "output=cdo_output.nc",
40         ... // other omitted parameters
41     ],
42     "dependencies": [
43         {
44             "argument": "input",
45             "task": "Export",
46             ... // other omitted parameters
47         }
48     ]
49 }
50 ]
51 }

```

Listing 9. Example of sub-workflow obtained from a checkpoint

The same label can be assigned to different checkpoints: also in this case a new PAV document is saved whenever a checkpoint passes, but each JSON file created overwrites the previous one associated with the same label; hence the last “passed” task is considered for the given checkpoint.

The ESDM-PAV runtime allows the user to retrieve the description of the “residual” experiment from a checkpoint, but also to submit the corresponding workflow without retrieving the new PAV document: only

the identifier of the original workflow and the checkpoint name are required. The ESDM-PAV Python module provides the features to submit a workflow from a given checkpoint (see Section 4.5).

Note that, in the current implementation, when a checkpoint is reached, the ESDM-PAV runtime only saves the JSON description of the tasks that have not been completed yet, but intermediate datasets and files are not considered. Thus, if these data are changed or deleted before repeating the execution, the experiment will fail. This feature can be used with all the available constructs except for the iterative loops, which are currently not supported.

4.4. ESDM-PAV Runtime implementation

The ESDM-PAV runtime is the main component (a C-based system) designed to execute experiments modelled with the ESDM-PAV schema and supports the different abstractions defined in the previous section, such as: conditionals, loops, error management, checkpointing, etc.

The runtime environment takes care of a) parsing and validating the experiment document to verify if the file follows the syntax and experiment definition rules b) building the corresponding execution graph based on the experiment specifications c) mapping the tasks to the related command and submitting their execution in the proper order, according to the dependencies d) monitoring the execution of the whole experiment. As previously mentioned, the runtime is able to handle not only pipelines of tasks, but also more complex Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) tasks.

More in detail, the ESDM-PAV runtime can:

- handle experiments using the full set of keywords and constructs defined in Section 4.3;
- manage the workflow execution concurrently and also update the status of each task composing the experiment workflow;
- address the execution of the PAV experiments distributed over multiple nodes.

The ESDM-PAV runtime system is publicly available on *GitHub*⁵ and is released under a FOSS licence (GPLv3).

Since the experiment schema has been defined based on the JSON schema already developed for the Ophidia framework, the base for the code of the runtime environment has been inherited from the Ophidia Server WfMS engine as well. This design choice has allowed us to reduce the time-to-solution and develop early in the project a first prototype of the runtime which was already robust and capable enough of handling complex workflow structures. From an implementation standpoint, with respect to the Ophidia original design, the ESDM-PAV runtime is able to operate without interacting with the data management system adopted by Ophidia for the system catalog (MySQL-based) and required by Ophidia Server to handle tasks, users, work sessions and the interaction with Ophidia framework, which also accesses the catalog. In fact, the runtime system exploits a light-weight SQLite database, accessed only by the runtime module, used to store information on task status used by the WfMS. Moreover, the ESDM-PAV runtime inherits all the interfaces of Ophidia Server (e.g., SOAP, WPS, etc.) and, therefore, it can interact with legacy Ophidia client applications, e.g., the Terminal and PyOphidia.

⁵ ESDM-PAV runtime code: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-runtime>

4.4.1. PAV tasks management

Concerning task management, the runtime system provides the means to monitor the general status of the experiment execution and of each associated task. The status information can be accessed from the ESDM-PAV Python module (see Section 4.5) to verify the progress of the experiment execution. As previously mentioned, the core of the runtime is based on the Ophidia server WfMS, so the definition of the status has been reprised and adapted from the Ophidia code. In particular, the status of a workflow can be any one of:

- *PENDING*: no task execution has begun yet;
- *RUNNING*: one or more tasks of the experiment are still running;
- *COMPLETED*: all tasks composing the experiment have been successfully completed;
- *ERROR*: one or more tasks composing the experiment have failed.

similarly, the status of each task can be as follows:

- *PENDING*: the task has been submitted but it is still waiting in its queue;
- *RUNNING*: the task is running on the computing resources;
- *WAITING*: the task is waiting for something (e.g., the availability of a file or ESDM data);
- *COMPLETED*: the task has been successfully completed;
- *ERROR*: the task has finished with an error;
- *SKIPPED*: the task has not been executed or resulted in a tolerable error (see Section 4.3.3).

The Python module uses the status information associated with each task, as well as the dependency information, to provide a graphical representation of the experiment execution progress.

Based on its configuration, the engine can support the execution of PAV experiment workflows on a single-node, where tasks are spawned as new processes on the node resources, as well as the remote execution of tasks to *scale their execution on multiple-nodes*. This feature aims to provide a higher degree of PAV experiments scalability allowing the execution (also concurrently) of the tasks composing a workflow on different nodes.

The runtime has thus been designed to support distributed execution scenarios. In such a design, the runtime is composed of three main actors:

- the *master runtime*, the central component managing the submission of tasks that are part of the experiment, based on their dependencies. This component also includes the *worker status manager* sub-component, which manages both workers and jobs status information (reported in a central SQLite database) by consuming update messages queued by the workers;
- the *worker runtime* component, which manages the actual execution of the PAV application. Multiple workers can be executed on different nodes to support distributed execution of tasks;
- a *queuing system*, which acts as a coordinator between the two components to manage task execution.

In order to improve resource utilisation and better balance the load over the various nodes, a *pull-based* approach has been used exploiting a message queue broker [21]. In this scenario, the communication between the various system components takes place by exchanging messages placed in the message queues and making the communication asynchronous. Each worker component requests a new task from the

queueing system as soon as it becomes available after the execution of the previous task, while the master will simply place the tasks in the task queue without worrying about assigning it to a specific worker.

A message queue system has been used to handle the interaction between the runtime master and worker components. Message queues are software components capable of containing messages to facilitate communication between different entities. Messages sent by sending systems are stored in queues until receiving systems consume them, so that the communication is asynchronous and managed independently by the two systems, which makes them decoupled and easily maintainable.

Note that during PAV experiment execution, further auxiliary queues are used for the internal management of the system besides the central message queue used for task management. The additional messages exchanged concern updates about the status of workers and tasks in processing. All worker update messages are processed by the worker status manager, a sub-process of the master that allows the runtime to apply cancellation policies for tasks in processing, if required. Thus, it is evident that the message queues play a central role in this system.

The message queue system used for the ESDM-PAV is the *RabbitMQ* [22]. RabbitMQ is an open-source message-broker software created to exploit the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) [23] but it was later extended with various plugins to allow the usage of other protocols. The system provides support for fault-tolerance thanks to message recovery and allows exchanging messages in distributed applications, decoupling the communication between sender and recipient.

Figure 2 shows a view of the revised ESDM-PAV runtime internal design: (i) after the experiment workflow is translated to the associated task graph, (ii) the runtime (master) submits the various tasks to the queueing system in the proper order, (iii) the queueing system in turn places them in the task queue (iv) until some worker becomes available for the execution and queries the system for a new task, (v) once the task is assigned to the worker, it notifies its state (and related updates) to the runtime master during execution until its completion.

The notification system shown in Figure 2 allows the runtime to understand when a task is running or completed, along with its exit status, whether successful or in error. Based on this information, the runtime is able to start the execution of new (dependent) tasks and to report the end of the workflow to the original caller. It is worth noting that the runtime has two different views of the tasks status: an applicative view and a processing one. The *Catalog* database contains status information about tasks processed by the runtime and then sent to the queueing system, while the *Status* database contains all information about tasks that the running workers are currently processing. Therefore, this second database contains a subset of tasks of the first one since it contains only information on the tasks consumed by the task queue and still not completed.

Figure 2. Schematisation of the ESDM-PAV runtime system internals for multi-node experiment execution

It is important to mention that each task is associated with the execution of one of the available PAV applications integrated in the system, based on the ESDM-PAV runtime master selection. There are application-specific plugins for the various tools used for the execution, so that the worker is able to transfer application-specific parameters to the tool (e.g., the number of threads for CDO operators running in multi-threading mode). See Section 4.7 for additional details on this point. Each task can also be executed with multiple cores/threads if the related PAV application supports this level of parallelism.

The approach followed in the design of the PAV runtime allows easy horizontal scaling of the execution of experiments on multiple machines by simply starting additional worker components on new nodes; thanks to the pull-based solution employed, new workers can be added to the configuration without affecting the rest of the setup. It is worth noting that each worker can also run more than one task concurrently, based on the software component configuration.

New workers components can be started via a simple Python command line tool called “*esdm-pav-worker*”. The tool has been designed to manage the start and shutdown of worker components at run-time, considering a good compatibility with different HPC scheduling systems (see Section 4.4.2 for additional details on this point), since it is based on bash scripts that are easily customisable.

The “*esdm-pav-worker*” Python CLI provides a very simple interface as it just requires performing the action “*start/shutdown*” and selecting the “*number*” of worker components for the action. Since the master runtime is only responsible for transmitting tasks to the queueing system that, in turn, simply places them in a queue,

all tasks queued will remain unprocessed until a runtime worker consumes and processes them. Thus, in order to process all tasks, one or more runtime workers have to be started. During a typical analysis experiment, it is possible to use the designed tool both to start workers at the beginning of the session and to shutdown them once all experiment tasks are processed. So, for example, to start ten workers to process tasks, the following command can be used:

```
$ esdm-pav-worker -a start -n 10
```

Similarly, to shut down the ten running worker components, the following command is used:

```
$ esdm-pav-worker -a shutdown -n 10
```

Note that a running worker can be shut down at any time and it is also possible to shut down a subset of running workers. Moreover, it is possible to omit the last argument when only a single worker has to be started/shut down.

4.4.2. Integration with HPC schedulers

To support compatibility with different scheduling systems, the pav-worker interface has been designed with a set of configurable submission and deployment recipes (i.e., bash scripts), which control the startup and shutdown of the worker components. The worker deployment has been successfully tested on LSF, a batch scheduling system typically used in HPC, but the solution should be easily exploitable also with other similar solutions.

Figure 3 describes how and in what order the runtime components interact with each other in a deployment and execution scenario.

As depicted in the figure, both the runtime system and the workers are initially instantiated (for the time required to run the PAV Experiment) by the user via the *command line tool* presented above. The *master runtime* is the component that takes care of the worker deployment process by interfacing with the *HPC scheduler*. Although the *queueing system* and the *worker status manager sub-component* are running on the “*Compute Node Master*”, neither is involved in the deployment process. Once one or more workers start, the *master runtime* will have proof of this since it will receive both the *HPC scheduler* response and status updates from workers that have been started. As soon as workers are available, a PAV Experiment can be submitted and executed using the Python client (see Section 4.5). The runtime will then start interacting with the *queueing system* and the workers connected to it will both consume and process tasks in a pull manner by constantly updating the runtime master component on the processing status. Finally, all workers deployed can be shutdown using the same command line tool; the runtime will ask the HPC scheduler to shut down the running workers and each interested worker will update the runtime with their status.

Figure 3. Sequence diagram of a worker life-cycle on HPC compute node

4.5. ESDM-PAV Python module

The ESDM-PAV Client is a Python module providing the features to model and execute a PAV experiment implemented with the aforementioned experiment schema. The package is available on Github⁶. The main features provided by the module are:

⁶ ESDM-PAV client code: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client>

- *The API for creating PAV experiments*: it implements two classes (i.e. *Experiment* and *Task*) with a set of methods to help users create PAV experiment documents, handle the underlying PAV schema transparently and make sure that the proper syntax and rules are followed. Moreover, it implements the methods to load and store the *experiment document* as a JSON file;
- *The API for managing PAV experiments execution*: it provides a class (i.e., *Workflow*) with a set of methods to manage PAV workflow execution. In particular, it allows users to submit the defined PAV experiment workflow directly from a Python script or notebook, monitor its progress and, in case, cancel the execution;
- *A command line interface for workflow submission*: it represents a CLI for submitting a PAV experiment document in JSON format. The Python client has been implemented in place of a C-based one in order to improve tool portability and usability, and to avoid having to build the client code in each environment.

The *Workflow* class and the client interact with the ESDM-PAV runtime for the execution of the experiment, taking care of substituting the argument at execution time. The communication between the ESDM-PAV Python module and the ESDM-PAV runtime is based on a TCP/IP architecture inherited from the Ophidia Server, which relies on PyOphidia client class for the instantiation of the connection.

The module also provides the Python scripts to easily install it, as well as the inline documentation and unit testing for the main methods. The following subsections delve into the details of the various features available and provide some usage examples of the Python module.

4.5.1. Experiment modelling

The *Experiment* and *Task* modules, as previously mentioned, provide the functions to build a PAV experiment document and store it in the JSON format introduced in Section 4.3.

A new task of the experiment document can be specified with the *Task* class constructor (the arguments have the meaning defined in Section 4.3):

```
t1 = Task(name="Sample task", type="ophidia", operator="oph_reduce",
         on_error="skip", arguments={"operation": "avg"})
```

whereas a dependency on a given task can be added with the specific method:

```
t2 = Task(name="Sample task2", type="ophidia", operator="oph_aggregate",
         arguments={"operation": "max"})
t2.addDependency(t1, argument="cube")
```

The “*cube*” argument in the dependency means that the output of task *t1* will be used as input for the “*cube*” argument in task *t2*. Multiple dependencies can be associated with the same task and each task can have multiple dependencies linking it.

A new experiment document can be created with the *Experiment* class constructor specifying the global experiment arguments, as described in Section 4.3:

```
e1 = Experiment(name="Sample experiment", author="sample author",
               abstract="sample abstract", nthreads=1)
```

Tasks can then be added to the experiment definition with the function:

```
e1.addTask(t1)
```

To simplify the creation of tasks and related dependencies, the *Experiment* module can be used to directly create and add a task to the experiment definition:

```
t2 = e1.newTask(name="Sample task2", type="ophidia", operator="oph_aggregate",
               on_error="skip", arguments={"operation": "max"},
               dependencies={t1:"cube"})
```

The *dependencies* argument can be used to specify a list of dependencies in a compact format using a Python dictionary structure. Each dependency can be defined by specifying the task object to be linked (e.g., task *t1*) followed by the input argument in the dependent task (e.g., the *cube* argument in task *t2*), with the format *task: "input argument"*.

A task within an experiment can be accessed by using the object variable (e.g., *t1*) or by retrieving the object from the experiment definition through the task name, with:

```
t1 = e1.getTask(taskname="Sample task")
```

Experiments can also be composed by reusing a whole experiment definition by means of the *subexperiment* method.

```
t3 = e1.newSubexperiment(name="new_subexperiment", experiment=e2,
                        params={}, dependencies=[{t1:"cube"}])
```

The experiment definition structure can be checked with the *check* method to validate the experiment definition, for example in terms of proper syntax and dependency consistency. The method returns either True/False, depending on whether the workflow is valid or not and can display the experiment structure as a static graph. It also supports the integration with Jupyter Notebook to graphically display the structure. Thanks to this method, the user can verify the experiment structure before submitting the execution:

```
e1.check(visual=True)
```

The argument “visual” (set to True by default) can be used to visualise the experiment definition graph as a picture, besides returning the validation result.

Once the experiment definition is completed, it can be stored as a JSON file, for example called “sample_experiment.json” in order to be reused later with the following method:

```
e1.save("sample_experiment.json")
```

A whole experiment object can also be created by loading a JSON document compliant with the experiment definition schema (see Section 4.3) with the proper method:

```
e1 = Experiment.load("sample_experiment.json")
```

These interfaces provide a complete set of features for the definition of workflows with all the abstractions supported by the JSON schema. However, higher-level interfaces targeting increased usability of flow control operations are envisioned for future versions of the module.

Example

Listing 10 shows a complete usage example of Experiment and Task modules used for the creation of a simple PAV experiment of four CDO tasks. It first specifies a post-processing operation with CDO (a regridding on a NetCDF [24] file), then three independent CDO time aggregation tasks are defined, in Lines 11-25, on the ESDM output of the first task to perform different statistical aggregations.

```

1  from esdm_pav_client import Experiment, Task
2
3  e1 = Experiment(name="CDO PAV experiment example",
4                 author="ESiWACE2",
5                 abstract="Example of PAV experiment with CDO")
6  t1 = e1.newTask(name="Regrid",
7                 type="cdo",
8                 operator='-remapbil,r90x45',
9                 arguments={'input': 'path/to/infile.nc',
10                          'output': 'esdm://out_container'})
11 t2 = e1.newTask(name="Max",
12                type="cdo",
13                operator='-timmax',
14                arguments={'output': 'esdm://container_max'},
15                dependencies={t1:'input'})
16 t3 = e1.newTask(name="Min",
17                type="cdo",
18                operator='-timmin',
19                arguments={'output': 'esdm://container_min'},
20                dependencies={t1:'input'})
21 t4 = e1.newTask(name="Avg",
22                type="cdo",
23                operator='-timavg',
24                arguments={'output': 'esdm://container_avg'},
25                dependencies={t1:'input'})
26
27 e1.save("example.json")
28 e1.check()

```

Listing 10. Simple PAV experiment implemented with the ESDM-PAV Python module

The final line (Line 27) is used to “check” the experiment structure before its execution. The related output obtained from this method is shown in Figure 4. Additional usage examples can be found in the module repository⁷ and in Section 4.5.4.

⁷ ESDM-PAV Python Client readme: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client/blob/master/README.md>

Figure 4. Visualisation of the static workflow graph associated with the experiment defined in Listing 10. This visualization is automatically generated by the last call in Listing 10 (Line 28).

4.5.2. Execution management

The *Workflow* module provides the features to fully support PAV experiment workflows execution, including monitoring progress and cancelling the execution.

Workflow objects can be instantiated starting from an *Experiment object* to run a new workflow or from a workflow identifier to link a previously submitted workflow; this second option is useful to reprise the monitoring of the workflow execution in a different moment. The following can be used for the two options:

```
w1 = Workflow(e1)
w1 = Workflow(1)
```

Once a new workflow has been instantiated from an experiment definition, it can be executed with the “*submit*” method. This function submits the experiment definition to the ESDM-PAV runtime for its execution. The method can optionally take as input the arguments to be replaced in the PAV document at run-time, if these have been defined in the experiment description, using the *\$N* variable syntax (as shown in Lines 22 and 35 in Listing 2). The function is non-blocking, so as soon as the experiment is submitted a workflow identifier will be returned. This could be used to later manage workflow execution from a different application or script.

```
id = w1.submit("2")
```

The workflow identifier can also be accessed directly from the Python object properties, once the workflow has been submitted, by accessing:

```
w1.workflow_id
```

Moreover, a workflow can also be started from a *checkpoint*, as described in Section 4.3.4, by providing the checkpoint name. For example, the following command generates and sends the PAV document shown in

Listing 9 in order to repeat the execution of the workflow described in Listing 8 from the checkpoint called “exported”:

```
w1.submit("2", checkpoint="exported")
```

The workflow execution can also be cancelled with the following method:

```
w1.cancel()
```

Finally, the *monitor* method allows users to check the experiment execution progress and the status of all the tasks composing the experiment; the status can be displayed in a simple textual format or in a graphical format, similar to what shown by the *check* method. The result can also be easily integrated and displayed within Jupyter Notebooks. This function supports continuous progress monitoring by periodically updating the status visualisation at a configurable interval.

```
w1.monitor(frequency=100, iterative=True, visual_mode=True)
```

The function takes 3 optional parameters:

- the “frequency” parameter, i.e., an integer that determines how often the status is updated (default value is 10);
- the “iterative” parameter (Boolean), which defines if the status has to be periodically updated (with “True”) or not (with “False”); default value is “True”;
- the “visual_mode” (Boolean). If “True” (the default value), the status will be displayed via a graph (as in Figure 5), otherwise the status will be provided by text.

Example

Listing 11 shows an example of usage of the Workflow module starting from the experiment defined in Listing 10. In Line 3, the experiment workflow is submitted to the ESDM-PAV runtime, then its status can be monitored with the monitor function (Line 5) and, if necessary, the workflow can be cancelled in Line 7.

```
1 from esdm_pav_client import Workflow, Experiment
2 w1 = Workflow(e1)
3 w1.submit()
4
5 w1.monitor(frequency=10, iterative=False, visual_mode=True)
6
7 w1.cancel()
```

Listing 11. Simple PAV experiment implemented with the ESDM-PAV Python module

In the case of Listing 11, the “*monitor*” method is used to get a single snapshot of the experiment status and, thus, iterative is set to “False” (Line 5). The related execution graph is shown in Figure 5, where colors have been used to more easily identify the status of the various tasks as defined in Section 4.4.1. In particular, the *green* color is used for COMPLETED tasks, the *red* color for ERROR tasks, the *orange* color for RUNNING tasks and the *light orange* color for PENDING tasks, the *cyan* color for WAITING task, the *yellow* color for SKIPPED tasks; tasks not yet ready for execution are shown in *gray*. In the case displayed in the figure, all tasks have been successfully completed.

Figure 5. Visualisation of the status of a workflow as provided by ESDM-PAV Python module when executing the experiment defined in Listing 10. The green color shows that all steps have been completed successfully.

4.5.3. Python CLI

The features to submit an experiment, monitor its progress and cancel the execution have also been included in the Python command line interface (CLI) for users to control the PAV experiment execution without having to implement a Python script or Notebook. The different options supported by the CLI can be shown by running:

```
esdm-pav-client -h
```

The following snippet (Listing 12) shows the usage of the CLI tool for the non-blocking execution of an experiment defined in the *myexperiment.json* PAV document (Line 1); the synchronous execution with status checking, through *-s option* (Line 4); and then the cancellation of the experiment execution (Line 8).

```

1  $ esdm-pav-client -w myexperiment.json inputarg
2  Submitted! Workflow id = 1
3
4  $ esdm-pav-client -w myexperiment.json inputarg -s
5  Submitted! Workflow id = 2
6  COMPLETED
7
8  $ esdm-pav-client -c -i 2
  
```

Listing 12. Example of use of the ESDM-PAV CLI

4.5.4. Test cases

A set of initial examples has been implemented with the ESDM-PAV Python module with the goal of testing the features provided by the runtime and evaluating the level of integration achieved. The current set of tests focuses on verifying the main constructs provided by the PAV runtime with simple workflows. Larger-scale

tests on real PAV experiments will be implemented in the remainder of the project and reported in deliverable D5.3.

This section shows some of the test cases implemented and executed via the Python class within Jupyter Notebooks. In particular, two PAV experiment examples are reported: (i) a parallel execution of sequences of tasks on multiple NetCDF files using also the ESDM middleware and (ii) a set of tasks applied as soon as ESDM data become available.

```
In [ ]: from esdm_pav_client import Workflow, Experiment

e1 = Experiment(
    name="Example of parallel branches",
    author="ESIWACE2",
    abstract="Parallel exec example",
    exec_mode="async"
)

t1 = e1.newTask(name="Start loop",
               type="control",
               operator='for',
               arguments={"key": "index", "values": "$1", "parallel": "yes"})
t2 = e1.newTask(name="Regrid",
               type="cdo",
               operator='- remapbil,r360x180',
               arguments={'input': 'tasmax_input_@{index}.nc', 'output': 'esdm://tasmax_@{index}', 'force': 'yes'},
               dependencies={t1:''})
t3 = e1.newTask(name="Import",
               type="ophidia",
               operator='oph_importesdm',
               arguments={'measure': 'tasmax', 'imp_dim': 'time', 'nfrag': '1', 'ioserver': 'ophidiaio_memory'},
               dependencies={t2:'input'})
t4 = e1.newTask(name="Reduce",
               type="ophidia",
               operator='oph_reduce',
               arguments={'operation': 'avg'},
               dependencies={t3:'cube'})
t5 = e1.newTask(name="End loop",
               type="control",
               operator='endfor',
               arguments={},
               dependencies={t4:'cube'})
t6 = e1.newTask(name="Merge",
               type="ophidia",
               operator='oph_mergecubes2',
               arguments={'dim': "new_dim"},
               dependencies={t5:'cubes'})
t7 = e1.newTask(name="Export",
               type="ophidia",
               operator='oph_exportnc',
               arguments={'output': 'tasmax_output.nc'},
               dependencies={t6:'cube'})
t8 = e1.newTask(name="Paraview script",
               type="generic",
               operator='plot_tas_paraview.py',
               arguments={"output": "paraview_res.png"},
               dependencies={t7:'input'})

w1 = Workflow(e1)
w1.submit("2015|2016|2017|2018|2019|2020")
w1.monitor(frequency=1, iterative=True, visual_mode=True)
```

Figure 6. PAV experiment Notebook example for the “for” construct

In the first case, a simple usage example for the “for” control task through the Python module is shown in the figure above (Figure 6). In this notebook, a PAV experiment consisting of a set of CDO and Ophidia operators run on six NetCDF files is defined. In particular, for each file, a (i) regridding operation is performed with the remap CDO operator (“bilinear remap”) and (ii) then, each remap output (ESDM container) is imported in Ophidia with the “oph_importesdm” and (iii) a data reduction operation (oph_reduce operators) to compute the average is run.

This sequence of operations is run concurrently on the maximum near-surface air temperature variable (*tasmax*) from six different input NetCDF files, each corresponding to a single year of daily values from the

CMCC-ESM2 model [1] (SSP585 experiment) CMIP6 dataset [2], from 2015 to 2020. Finally, all output cubes from the last task within the “for” construction are merged to build a single output cube using the “oph_mergecubes2” Ophidia operator. The obtained result is then exported in an NetCDF file using the “oph_exportnc” Ophidia operator and the output file is used to produce a picture (shown in the deliverable front page) using the “generic” operator with a ParaView-based Python script. Figure 7 shows the execution graph related to this experiment (where the various colours represent the different states).

Figure 7. Visualisation of the execution graph associated with the “for” experiment

The second case, in Figure 8, shows an example of the “wait” construct again from the Python module. The notebook in Figure 8a presents the definition of a PAV experiment where a set of tasks is applied on a part of an ESDM container as soon as the data become accessible. After (i) the requested portion of ESDM data becomes available, (ii) this is loaded directly from ESDM into Ophidia and then (iii) processed via an Ophidia data aggregation operator, the (iv) final result is stored back as an ESDM container. It is noteworthy that the second task, the data import in Ophidia, also applies an in-flight analytics operation (the average) directly when the stream of data is retrieved from the ESDM system, as explained in detail in Section 4.6. Figure 8b shows the repeated execution graph; the first task is coloured in cyan since it is waiting for the ESDM data availability.

Figure 8. PAV experiment example for the “wait” construct: a) the experiment implementation and b) the related execution graph are shown

4.6. In-flight analytics via ESDM

Big data analytics often requires complex operations to be executed on input datasets: interpolation, regridding, low pass filtering, etc. These operations can be performed only by nodes having adequate compute resources, cores, graphics processors, etc. Hence, a huge amount of data often needs to be transferred from data nodes, optimised for storage, to compute nodes, which process them, and then back

to data nodes, to save the final results. This data transfer involves delay and bandwidth utilisation, as well as energy consumption. However, innovative active storage solutions could be used to reduce data transfer and move parts of the processing on the storage back-end. In these cases, the amount of data to be loaded by compute nodes can be reduced as one or more simple operations could be executed directly by storage nodes before transferring the resulting data. For instance, this could be applied if the first operation to be executed is data selection or data reduction. Clearly, storage nodes are not well suited to perform heavy computations such as *fast fourier transforms* or *multidimensional splines*, however their local processors could be effectively used to evaluate simple operations like data averages, or filter operations in case the next steps of the analytics workflow need only processed values instead of full raw data. Transfer of these pre-processed data is quite faster as the data are smaller in size. An approach that includes this type of pre-processing, where the storage is *active*, is called *in-flight data analytics*.

In the context of the ESDM-PAV runtime, it has been decided to integrate the in-flight analytics directly at the level of PAV applications and enable these features from the PAV experiment document. To support in-flight data analytics, the features of the ESDM library are exploited to apply a *compute kernel* on data to be loaded from storage, and to read the corresponding results only, using the *esdm_read_stream*. As reported in [14], this extension to the ESDM API can be used to read an ESDM dataset and to register the compute kernel, possibly offloading the computation to the storage backend. When it is called, instead of reading the data, the function *esdm_read_stream* calls on the storage to apply the kernel operations and return the results of the computation to the caller.

In the current implementation, the signature of the function *esdm_read_stream* is:

```
esdm_status esdm_read_stream(
    esdm_dataset_t *dataset,
    esdm_dataspace_t *space,
    void *user_ptr,
    esdm_stream_func_t *stream_func,
    esdm_reduce_func_t *reduce_func);
```

where *dataset* and *space* define the dataset to be loaded, and *user_ptr* is the pointer to a user-defined struct containing metadata to be passed to the kernel (e.g. input parameters). Finally, the functions *stream_func* and *reduce_func* define the specific compute kernel to be registered.

A kernel performs a typical map-reduce operation. The function *stream_func*, whose interface is

```
void *stream_func(
    esdm_dataspace_t *space,
    void *buff,
    void *user_ptr,
    void *esdm_fill_value);
```

accesses an ESDM data fragment (*buff*), processes it by exploiting the information carried by the user-defined struct *user_ptr* and returns intermediate results within a user-defined struct (called *stream_func_out* in the following). This phase could be considered as a mapping phase, when raw data are transformed directly on the active storage before any data transfer to compute nodes.

The signature of the function *reduce_func* is:

```
void *reduce_func(
    esdm_dataspace_t *space,
    void *user_ptr,
    void *stream_func_out);
```

This function processes the user-defined struct *stream_func_out*, representing the outputs of *stream_func*, to produce the final output to be returned to *esdm_read_stream* caller: the function is applied several times, once for each ESDM data fragment into which the input ESDM dataset has been split. This phase could be considered as a reduction phase: the intermediate results obtained during the mapping phase are gathered to produce the final dataset that will be returned and will represent the (few) data actually moved from the active storage to the compute nodes.

A number of analytical kernels have been developed as an extension of the Ophidia platform, one of the PAV target applications considered in the context of the ESIWACE2 project. In particular, the operator OPH_IMPORTESDM, designed within WP4, has been enhanced with the read-streaming option of the ESDM library in order to exploit active storage capabilities while loading an ESDM dataset, and to implement simple computations during this phase. The current set of features supported by the operator allows applying selection, statistical analysis and mathematical functions.

For instance, the user could select the time series associated with a specific space point (subsetting), evaluate the average of that series by using the operation ESDM_FUNCTION_AVG (reduction) and retrieve the mean value only (loading). In such a case, to adopt the analytical kernel while converting an ESDM dataset into an Ophidia datacube, the user simply has to set the argument *operation* of OPH_IMPORTESDM to the related name. Listing 13 shows the JSON code of the task associated with this example. The *latitude* and *longitude* dimensions on which the subsets are applied (Line 8), including the coordinates of the selected point (40° latitude and 20° longitude - Line 9) and the *avg* operation to be carried out by the active storage (Line 11) are specified while importing the ESDM dataset named *pressure* from the container *esdm://pressure.nc*. Clearly, the label *avg* is associated with the operation ESDM_FUNCTION_AVG.

```

1      {
2      "name": "Import",
3      "type": "ophidia",
4      "operator": "oph_importesdm",
5      "arguments": [
6      "input=esdm://pressure.nc",
7      "measure=pressure",
8      "subset_dims=lat|lon",
9      "subset_filter=40|20",
10     "subset_type=coord",
11     "operation=avg"
12     ]
13     }
```

Listing 13. Example of a task using in-flight analytics.

4.7. PAV plugin implementation

As depicted in Figure 1, the runtime system is designed to support, and to be extended with, additional PAV tools and software through the definition of plugins. The current version is able to support both Ophidia and CDO operators along with other command line-based tools through a generic plugin. Thanks to the generic plugin, a preliminary integration of ParaView in the PAV workflow, through scripts for non-interactive visualisation, has been made possible with the current runtime version.

In general, the plugin of a PAV application implements the following features:

- to provide an interface between task description in JSON format and input parameters of the application: the module parses the task arguments set in the experiment description and sets the corresponding arguments for the tool;
- to send notifications to ESDM-PAV runtime when task execution begins as well as when it ends, thus allowing workflow management;
- to format application outputs in JSON format, if necessary;
- to support error management.

Most of Ophidia operators were designed to roughly provide these features, for this reason the base design of a plugin is that of an operator [25]. Through this approach it was possible to easily support all the Ophidia operators also for the runtime.

However, a number of adaptations have been made to Ophidia operators in order to adhere to the ESDM-PAV experiment schema. In particular, the “input” and “output” argument names have been added to the Ophidia import and export operators to provide the same interface for all the tasks (i.e., CDO and Ophidia) working on input and output files or ESDM containers. Besides this, a specific plugin for CDO operators has also been implemented based on the notification-based approach already used for the Ophidia operators, in order to communicate the execution status to the runtime engine. The Ophidia extensions have been implemented in the Ophidia repositories.

The plugin designed for CDO allows the ESDM-PAV runtime to support most of the CDO operators within PAV experiments. In particular, the runtime handles all the operators having one output file (or ESDM container) or none, allowing the user to set it as the input for other tasks by exploiting the option “dependencies” as reported in Section 4.3. CDO operators that admit more than one output file (e.g. the command “*splityear*”) can also be executed, but the user cannot employ the option “dependencies” to assign output files as the inputs for other tasks, since it is not possible to easily predict beforehand the number of output that will be generated by the operator. In this case, the user should set the arguments of these tasks to the appropriate file names explicitly.

From an implementation point-of-view, the CDO plugin is an Ophidia operator, named OPH_CDO, acting as a wrapper for CDO commands. In addition, the plugin includes the modules to send notifications to the ESDM-PAV runtime and to handle the JSON interface (parsing input and formatting output).

The plugin has the following arguments:

- **command:** name of the CDO operator or list of “combining operators” to be executed;
- **input:** list of input file names;

	Page 45	
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- **output:** output file name (at least one file); the argument is not considered in case no output is produced;
- **skip_output:** flag set to “yes” in case no output is produced;
- **nthreads:** number of OpenMP threads to be activated (for the operator supporting multithreading).

It is worth noting that, in the JSON schema of an experiment, the field “operator” of CDO-type tasks corresponds to the argument “command” of OPH_CDO, so that the ESDM-PAV runtime is able to set all the arguments of OPH_CDO and submit the operator. In particular, the values of arguments “input” and “output” can automatically be set by means of the option “dependencies” in case input files (or ESDM containers) are produced by other tasks and output files have to be processed by other tasks. Finally, the parameter “nthreads” corresponds to the option “-P” of the CDO tool.

For a single CDO operator, the CDO plugin builds the actual command to be executed simply by appending the input file list and output file (if specified) to the argument “command” of OPH_CDO. Hence, the CDO operators performing respectively the sum of a constant value to *ifile* and the sum of the variables from *ifile1* and *ifile2*:

```
cdo -addc,1 ifile ofile
cdo -add ifile1 ifile2 ofile
```

can be specified by the CDO-type tasks in Listing 14.

```

1  {
2    "name": "CDO",
3    "type": "cdo",
4    "operator": "-addc,1",
5    "arguments": [
6      "input=ifile",
7      "output=ofile"
8    ]
9  },
10 {
11  "name": "CDO",
12  "type": "cdo",
13  "operator": "-add",
14  "arguments": [
15    "input=ifile1|ifile2",
16    "output=ofile"
17  ]
18 }
```

Listing 14. Example of tasks with CDO operators

In case of operator combination, the plugin provides a simple schema for the field “operator” to assign input files to the corresponding CDO operator. In practice, instead of setting the file name, the user has to set the index of the file in the input list (argument “input”). For instance, the following command concatenates a set of operators to perform (i) the time average over all the time steps on *ifile1* and (ii) the daily average on *ifile2* and (iii) subtracts the result of the first operation from the result of the second one:

```
cdo -sub -dayavg ifile2 -timavg ifile1 ofile
```

can be coded as a CDO-type task in a PAV document like in Listing 15.

Note that, if the index of an input file is considered at least once within the field “operator”, the plugin does not append the file name to the final command to be executed (as reported above). The plugin appends only the file names listed in “input” whose index is not reported in the field “operator”. Hence, in the previous example, the value of the field “operator” could also be set to “-sub -dayavg %2 -timavg” : in this case the filename *ifile1* would be appended to the command (before output filename) because there is no index %1 in field “operator”.

```

1  {
2    "name": "CDO",
3    "type": "cdo",
4    "operator": "-sub -dayavg %2 -timavg %1",
5    "arguments": [
6      "input=ifile1|ifile2",
7      "output=ofile"
8    ]
9  }

```

Listing 15. Example of a task with CDO a combination of operators

A more complex example of CDO command with combination is

```
cdo -add -merge [ -apply,"-addc,1" [ ifile1 ifile1 ifile2 ifile3 ] ] -sin ifile2
ofile
```

In this example of concatenation of operators: (i) the sine function is applied to the fields of *ifile2*, whereas (ii) the same operation is applied on *ifile1*, *ifile1*, *ifile2* and *ifile3* (adding a constant to the fields in each file) and at the end (iii) all the datasets are merged together in *ofile*. The corresponding task in the PAV experiment document is reported in Listing 16.

```

1  {
2    "name": "CDO",
3    "type": "cdo",
4    "operator": "-add -merge [ -apply,'-addc,1' [ %1 $1 %2 %3 ] ] -sin %2",
5    "arguments": [
6      "input=ifile1|ifile2|ifile3",
7      "output=ofile"
8    ]
9  }

```

Listing 16. Example of a task with CDO nested operators

A plugin similar to OPH_CDO has been developed to integrate other command line solutions, such as ParaView (when used from a script) in the PAV workflow: OPH_GENERIC. Also in this case the plugin acts as a wrapper for the general commands, Python and bash scripts. It could be considered as a base template to implement other tool-specific plugins.

4.8. Software setup

This section provides a quick reference guide for the setup of the ESDM-PAV software components: (i) the ESDM-PAV runtime and the (ii) ESDM-PAV Python client module. With respect to the previous release, the

setup of the runtime is now more automated and a preliminary effort has been made to improve software portability through containerisation.

4.8.1. Portability of the solution

Portability represents an important software property that also defines how easily a software solution can be installed and deployed on different systems. To this end, software containers have increasingly been used by the community as a means of moving the whole software stack and its dependencies across different machines and systems [26]. Portability is also important for systems such as the proposed runtime as it can allow the software to be ported to different HPC infrastructures.

In the case of the ESDM-PAV runtime, the evaluation of HPC-friendly containerisation technologies has been performed, i.e., solutions that can be deployed on HPC clusters without security and permission limitations, since the target is the execution of large-scale PAV experiments on HPC infrastructures. The technology selected for this purpose is *Singularity* [27].

Hence, a preliminary containerisation of some components of the runtime software with Singularity has been carried out to evaluate the feasibility of the approach. In particular, the runtime master component in single-node setup has been containerised, mainly for testing purposes, and some tests of execution have been successfully completed. Further tests will follow in this direction in the remainder of the project with the aim of targeting the full containerisation of the ESDM-PAV runtime environment and making the portability of the solution easier on different HPC environments.

4.8.2. Setup of the ESDM-PAV Runtime

The ESDM-PAV runtime is a C-based component and, hence, it needs to be built from source code on the target infrastructure. *GNU Autotools* (Autoconf, Automake, etc.) are used to support the building and installation phase.

The ESDM-PAV runtime requires a number of dependencies for its setup. Hence, before installing the code the following packages are required:

- *openssl* devel libraries
- *curl* and related devel libraries
- *libXML2* devel libraries
- *jansson* and related devel libraries
- *sqlite* and related devel libraries
- *ESDM* library
- *GNU Matheval library*
- *Ophidia and CDO*
- *RabbitMQ server* (required only in multi-node setup)
- *RabbitMQ C client library* (required only in multi-node setup)
- *libssh2 and libssh2-devel* (required only in multi-node setup)

Most of the libraries and tools can be installed from the Linux operating system package managers, such as yum (CentOS) or apt-get (Debian). Other modules can be installed or built following the instructions provided on the official documentation pages:

- Instructions for the *ESDM* library are available at: <https://github.com/ESIWACE/esdm>;
- *GNU Matheval*, required for the selection statement can be built from source <http://ftp.gnu.org/gnu/libmatheval/>;
- Ophidia can be installed following: <http://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/admin/index.html>;
- Documentation for the setup of CDO: <https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/wiki#Download-Compile-Install>;
- In case of the multi-node setup, *RabbitMQ server* must be set up and configured <https://www.rabbitmq.com/download.html>. The link also provides the instructions to install, configure and start the server instance according to Linux distribution;
- The *RabbitMQ C client* library, required for the interaction of the ESDM-PAV runtime with the queueing system, can be installed from the related GitHub repository: <https://github.com/alanxz/rabbitmq-c>.

Once all the dependencies are installed, the following instructions can be used to download the runtime from the GitHub repository and install the system for the single-node setup:

```
$ git clone https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-runtime.git --recurse-
submodules
$ cd esdm-pav-runtime
$ ./bootstrap
$ ./configure --prefix=$prefix --with-matheval-path=/path/to/libmatheval --
disable-multi_node
$ make
$ make install
```

In case of multi-node setup, the previous configure line can be replaced with the following one:

```
$ ./configure --prefix=$prefix --with-librabbitmq-header-
path=/path/to/rabbitmqclib/include --with-librabbitmq-lib-
path=/path/to/rabbitmqclib/lib --with-matheval-path=/path/to/libmatheval --with-
netcdf-path=/path/to/netcdf
--with-esdm-path=/path/to/esdm
--with-ophidiaio-server-path=/path/to/ophidia-io-server
```

Once the code is built and installed the following script can be executed to finalise the configuration:

```
$ $prefix/sbin/esdm_pav_config.sh path/to/rabbitmqserver
```

Finally, the runtime can be started as follows and it operates as a service:

```
$ $prefix/bin/esdm_pav_runtime
```

The process is not a daemon, but it can be executed in background mode using “&”. In case of multi-node setup, all the following processes need instead to be started:

	Page	
	49	

```
$ path/to/rabbitmqserver/sbin/rabbitmq-server -detached
$ $prefix/bin/esdm_pav_runtime &
$ $prefix/bin/esdm_pav_runtime_dbmanager &
$ $prefix/bin/esdm_pav_runtime_worker &
```

The last command can be executed on each node used for the computation. It is worth mentioning that the “*esdm-pav-worker*” Python tool can be used to start worker components without running the “*esdm_pav_runtime_worker*” processes manually (as explained in Section 4.4.1).

An additional startup script is also provided to properly start the various executables in the right order. The “*master*” or “*worker*” options can be used to respectively start the server or worker executables only:

```
$ $prefix/sbin/run_esdm_pav.sh master/worker
```

The full procedure to install and set up the components and the reference to the dependencies is reported on the runtime GitHub repository⁸.

4.8.3. Installation of the ESDM-PAV Python Client

The ESDM-PAV Python client can be easily installed by using the usual Python *setuptools*. The module requires a number of Python dependencies:

- *pyophidia*
- *click*
- *graphviz*

These can be easily installed with this command:

```
$ pip3 install pyophidia click graphviz=0.14
```

To install the ESDM-PAV client, the following instructions can be used to download and install the module from the GitHub repository:

```
$ git clone https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client.git
$ cd esdm-pav-client
$ python setup.py install
```

Alternatively, *pip* package installer can also be used within the repo folder, in place of the last command, with the following:

```
$ pip install -e .
```

The module can then be used as shown in the examples in Section 4.5. The full installation procedure is also reported on the client module GitHub repository⁹.

⁸ ESDM-PAV runtime documentation:

<https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-runtime/blob/master/README.md>

⁹ ESDM-PAV Python client documentation:

<https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client/blob/master/README.md>

5. Abbreviations and acronyms

Term	Description
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
CDO	Climate Data Operators
CLI	Command Line Interface
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
ESDM	Earth-System Data Middleware
ESM	Earth System Modelling
FOSS	Free and open source software
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LSF	Load Sharing Facility
MS	Milestone
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
PAV	Post-processing, Analytics and Visualisation
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and Internet Protocol (IP)
WfMS	Workflow Management System
WP	Work Package
WPS	Web Processing System

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	Page	
	52	

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7. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Throughout the first part of the project, the design and development of the ESDM-PAV extensions have evolved towards a system able to orchestrate PAV applications on HPC instructions aiming to take into account the requirements of PAV applications. Various internal meetings also involving the ESDM team from WP4 have been held to progressively refine the developments and tackle potential difficulties.

8. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

As the volumes of data in scientific domains continue to rise, support for data-intensive science, besides the traditional compute-intensive science, has become key for future research advancements. To this end, the convergence of extreme data and HPC technologies within a single software ecosystem represents an enabling factor. Data analytics and visualisation are in fact expected to become an important part of the future extreme-scale HPC software infrastructure [28]. Solutions able to properly exploit the infrastructure to support High Performance Data Analytics applications, also in view of the availability of exascale supercomputers in the near future, are thus required.

The solutions proposed in this document try to address some of these challenges by providing a high-level interface to simplify the execution of heterogeneous PAV applications on top of HPC infrastructures, supporting distribution of data-oriented processing on the HPC computing-oriented architecture, and also aiming at reduced data movement through in-flight analytics by means of the ESDM system.

9. Sustainability

The activities reported in this deliverable represent the developments of the design initially described in the project milestones MS5.1 (from WP5) and MS4.1 (from WP4) reports. Moreover, these are also related to deliverable D4.1 “Advanced software stack for Earth system data”, and in general to WP4, since the ESDM-PAV runtime and in-flight analytics build directly upon the ESDM system development.

The integration of PAV applications is not trivial since these may target very different application scenarios. The approach used within WP5 for the development of the ESDM-PAV runtime tries, on one hand, to simplify the coexistence of different software programs in a single experiment through a general interface, while minimising, on the other hand, the changes required by the PAV applications. Moreover, having based part of the design on what was already available for Ophidia rather than starting from scratch, it was possible to develop a much more complete solution in terms of features provided.

While the usability of the PAV document JSON format is not perfect, it meets the purpose to be a human-readable and machine-readable intermediate representation for the workflow definition. With the integration of the different community tools such as CDO and Ophidia into one workflow, we believe their adoption in the community will be accelerated. In the long run, having an intermediate abstraction layer regardless of the implementing tool will foster platform-independence and performance too (as an inefficient implementation on one system can be swapped easily for a given step). In this direction, the implemented

	Page	
	54	

Python-based interface addresses software usability and should significantly simplify the use of the system by the users, ultimately further accelerating its adoption and exploitation by the community.

The software presented in this deliverable will be further improved throughout the ESIWACE2 project to address robustness, efficiency, portability and usability including wider adoption. Sustainability of ESDM (and in particular ESDM-PAV) will leverage a contribution by several partners and interest by the community to include further development of this software into new proposals.

10. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

10.1. Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

As for all the ESIWACE2 project deliverables, this document is made available to anyone interested via the Zenodo repository. The developed activities performed and the results achieved will be presented during community-based large events, such as the EGU conference, as well as during the training events organised as part of the project activities.

10.2. Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Participation in a workshop	Donatello Elia, "A HPDA-enabled environment for scalable climate data analysis", 6th ENES HPC Workshop	29 May 2020, Virtual/Hamburg (DE)	Scientific Community	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3964536	80
Participation in a workshop	Donatello Elia, "An HPC-enabled Data Science and Learning Environment for Climate Change Experiments at Scale", EXDCI-2 Virtual Workshop on AI and HPC convergence	26 November 2020, Virtual	Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4633367	45

Participation in a workshop	Donatello Elia, "Ophidia: High Performance Data Analytics framework for Climate Change at scale", IS-ENES3 Virtual workshop on requirements for a fast and scalable evaluation workflow	18-19 May 2021, Virtual	Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5535704	30
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10.3. Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <i>open access</i> be provided to this publication?

10.4. Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

All software and the related code developed for the ESDM extensions PAV applications are released under Open Source licences, such as: GPLv3 for the ESDM-PAV runtime, the PAV Python API and the extensions to the Ophidia framework; the ESDM is released under the LGPLv3 license.